

LIGHTWEIGHT AUTOENCODER CAPABILITIES FOR ON-BOARD IMAGE COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based models, such as AutoEncoder (AE) Neural Network (NN) models, for on-board compression of Remote Sensing (RS) Earth Observation (EO) images. The focus of NN-based on-board compression is on reducing the volume of data transmitted to the ground while preserving essential information. The study investigates the topic by considering two applications. The first one shows the advantages of shallow AEs in compressing Sentinel-2 images for a change detection application. The second one uses a Convolutional AE (CAE) for on-board image compression, including both a 2-dimensional (compression of image height and width) and a 3-dimensional (compression of image height, width, and depth) scenarios. This second application is the core of the Deep Compression Application on-board the Φ sat-2 CubeSat mission by European Space Agency (ESA). The complexity of the algorithms for hardware implementation was evaluated in detail. These applications highlight the potential of AI and DL techniques to optimize on-board data management.

INTRODUCTION

On-board processing is necessary to manage the huge volume of remote sensing data, enabling data selection and compression before ground transmission. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Deep Learning (DL) are powerful tools for extracting valuable information from complex data and optimizing operations on-board the space platforms. The rise of CubeSats has fostered research in this field, with missions such as Φ sat-1 and Φ sat-2 of the European Space Agency (ESA) demonstrating the practical benefits of on-board AI. Hardware advances in on-board AI accelerators are further supporting these developments. However, these systems require low-power consumption AI algorithms, that are instead known to be computationally heavy. Therefore, lightweight versions compatible with the target hardware must be developed [1].

Among the DL models, AutoEncoders (AEs) are commonly used for feature learning and data compression. AEs consist of an encoding part and a decoding part, with one or more hidden layers, and a middle bottleneck layer with fewer parameters than either input or output. The bottleneck layer forces a compressed knowledge representation of the original input and determines the Compression Ratio (CR), i.e., the ratio between the input size and the compressed size [2]. AEs are used here in two different applications. In the first application a fully connected AE model is used to extract the compressed representation of the original Sentinel-2 multi-temporal image couples in order to investigate the possibility to perform change detection on a compressed version of the input, instead of the original one. In a change detection application, only images with changes should be downloaded to the ground to save data. Due to limited on-board computational resources, change detection on a compressed version of the input image is explored. The choice to implement a fully connected network is mainly because change detection is a task that requires a complex on-board processing chain. It includes, for example, georeferencing and co-registration operations of the multi-temporal images. In comparison to deep convolutional models, fully connected networks are very light in terms of size and computational power [3]. In the second application a Convolutional AutoEncoder (CAE) model is used for the task of image compression on-board the satellites. The CAE separately uses the encoder and decoder part to encode the acquisitions on-board the platform and decode them on the ground. This allows for saving bandwidth in data transmission and eventually on-board

storage. Two different compression types are considered, and therefore two CAE models, that are 2-dimensional (2D) and 3-dimensional (3D) compression. In 2D compression single band acquisitions are considered, therefore images are compressed in terms of height and width, and the CAE input has a size of $patch\ height \times patch\ width \times 1$. Patch height and width are the dimension of the sub-images extracted from the original image in terms of pixels. In 3D compression, instead, all the acquisition bands are considered, and it also includes compression among bands. The CAE input in this case has a size of $patch\ height \times patch\ width \times number\ of\ bands$. These models were developed in the context of the Φ sat-2 mission by European Space Agency (ESA). Φ sat-2 was launched in August 2024 and is a 6U CubeSat equipped with a multispectral push-broom imager. CogniSat is the on-board AI processor unit that is capable to run different AI-based applications that can be monitored and controlled on the spacecraft during flight through a dedicated software, the NanoSat MO Framework. The AI on-board computer is built around the Neural Compute Stick (NCS) Intel Movidius Myriad 2 Vision Processing Unit (VPU), that provide high-performance and low power envelope compatible with the CubeSat standard [4], [5].

AE FOR FEATURE-BASED CHANGE DETECTION

AE Model and Dataset

As shown in Fig. 1, in the training phase, highlighted in red, the AE model is trained to reconstruct the original input image patch, i.e., smaller sub-images. During the inference, in blue, only the encoder part of the network is used to extract the image features from the bottleneck layer. This is done for the multi-temporal couples of image patches that are compared by calculating a dissimilarity measure in terms of Euclidean Distance (ED).

More in detail, the final AE architecture is modelled to reduce the data dimensionality of one order. Therefore, since the input consists of 1,024 units, each sub-image is represented with 32 components, that is the number of units in the bottleneck. The architecture stems from a trial-and-error approach and final performance analysis.

The encoder part of this model, therefore the part that would be executed on-board, has a size of 1.55 MB. This model can be considered appropriate for a typical on-board environment in terms of size, as it is smaller than the model described later, that was tested on a specific on-board hardware.

Sentinel-2 images depicting urban and suburban areas were collected to build the dataset, that was integrated with the Onera Satellite Change Detection (OSCD) dataset. The latter is a dataset for change detection which consists of Sentinel-2 registered pairs of images acquired over the same location at a temporal distance of 2-3 years [6]. The pixel-level change ground truth is also given, but the annotated changes focus on urban changes, such as buildings or roads, while natural changes, such as vegetation, sun exposure, and brightness conditions, are ignored. Therefore, a reference map based on the Change Vector Analysis (CVA) was created for the evaluation of the results [7]. The CVA method is a widely used change detection technique and may be affected by errors, but it was used in this case to generate supplementary maps that highlight natural changes. Dataset pre-processing steps include selection of the bands of interest, division into patches, reshape, and normalization. More particularly, the RGB bands, namely Sentinel-2 band 4, band 3, and band 2, were considered for each image. This is because they have the finer spatial resolution of 10 m and they have been proved suitable in various change detection techniques, especially the red band, in both vegetated and urban environment [8]. Then the images were divided into patches with a dimension of $32 \times 32 \times 1$ ($patch\ height \times patch\ width \times depth$). Depth is the number of acquisition bands or channels and is equal to 1 in this case since the three bands, i.e., bands 2, 3, and 4 of Sentinel-2, are considered separately to form the dataset. Then, each patch was reshaped into a one-dimensional vector of size $32 \times 32 \times 1 = 1,024$ in order to be input into the AE model. Finally, each patch was normalized in the 0-1 interval.

Fig. 1. AE feature-based change detection scheme

Dimensionality Reduction

The change detection analysis is executed on the smaller representation of the input image obtained by the AE and also by using the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) algorithm. DWT was used as a benchmark technique for performance analysis because it is widely used for image compression, for example, in JPEG 2000 compression standard. It is based on the use of digital filtering techniques by means of wavelets. In the DWT dimensionality reduction procedure, the input image patches are similarly obtained by splitting the test images into sub-images of size 32×32 pixels. The Haar filter was chosen as mother wavelet, and the number of decomposition level was set to 2 [9]. Fig. 2 aims at comparing the patch reconstruction with both techniques, AE and DWT. Fig. 2 (a) and (d) show the original test patches in the red band (i.e., band number 4), at the time t_1 and t_2 . Fig. 2 (b) and (e) illustrate the reconstructed patch obtained as the output of the AE and Fig. 2 (c) and (f) the DWT reconstruction. In this case, only the first 32 coefficients of DWT were extracted setting the remaining ones to zero.

Results

For the performance analysis, the patches obtained from the ground truth images were divided into three categories: patches without changes, patches with more than 10% of pixels changed, and patches with less than 10% of pixels changed. The graphs in Fig. 3 show the results obtained for a test image compressed by means of the AE and validated with the OSCD ground truth on the left side, and with the CVA reference map on the right side. For both methods, the EDs associated with no change patches are mainly localized in the lower part of the graph, while the EDs related to a high number of changed pixels are in the upper area.

From a quantitative perspective, results were evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, False Positive Rate (FPR), and F1 score. The Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve is also an effective method for evaluating algorithm performance, and the Area Under the Curve (AUC) measures the performance of the model for all possible change thresholds. However, in operational scenarios, threshold values should be defined previously in order for the algorithm to automatically discriminate between changed and no change patches. The definition of an optimal general value was found to be difficult because this value depends on the area represented in the image, and a scene with a predominant urban area may provide an optimal threshold value that is not the same as the one for a rural area. Therefore, most similar images in terms of land cover were selected from the dataset and, within this homogeneous class, the threshold value was determined with a statistical approach based on the best Recall score. This choice aims to minimize the number of missed alarms, that is, to reduce the number of images that report a change and could be missed. Table 1 summarizes the results obtained for a test image with AE and DWT reduction techniques and with OSCD and CVA validation. The AE reduction change detection performed better than the DWT.

CAE FOR IMAGE COMPRESSION

CAE Model and Dataset

A schematic representation of the CAE model is shown in Fig. 4: the purple part on the left shows the encoder part, to be executed on-board, while the green part on the right the decoder part, to be executed on the ground. The acquired images

Fig. 2. Comparison between the images reconstructed with AE and DWT: (a) Original patch at time t_1 ; (d) Original patch at time t_2 ; (b), (e) Patch reconstruction through the AE model; (c), (f) Patch reconstruction through DWT

Fig. 3. ED value (y-axis) related to each patch (x-axis). Each marker is coloured according to the change condition in the OSCD (right) and CVA (left) references

Table 1. Results evaluated in terms of Precision, Recall, F1 score and AUC using both OSCD ground truth and CVA reference map

Reference image	Precision		Recall		F1		AUC	
	AE	DWT	AE	DWT	AE	DWT	AE	DWT
OSCD	0.63	0.58	0.58	0.30	0.60	0.39	0.91	0.83
CVA	0.78	0.71	0.97	0.52	0.86	0.60	0.99	0.95

are processed in the encoder to obtain the compressed inputs, that are sent to the ground where they are restored by means of the decoder. The final definition of the model architecture was determined considering the compromise between reaching a significant compression and limiting information loss and the requirements imposed by the mission, especially in terms of model memory footprint and RAM usage. During training, a loss function based on Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), a well-known image quality index, was considered for the 2D model, while a loss function based on the combination of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and SSIM was considered for the 3D model. The other main differences between the models are shown in Table 2.

The dataset used is based on Sentinel-2 acquisitions that were converted to simulate the Φ sat-2 acquisitions. Pre-processing steps also include normalization and tiling into patches with a dimension of 256×256 pixels.

Hardware Implementation

The performance achieved by the 2D and 3D AI compression models were evaluated for the on-board hardware, that is

Fig. 4. CAE structure. The original input image is fed into the encoder part to extract the compressed representation through the bottleneck layer (on-board execution, in purple). The image is reconstructed in the decoder part (on the ground execution, in green)

Table 2. Comparison between 2D and 3D CAE models

	2D Model	3D Model
Model input size	$256 \times 256 \times 1$	$256 \times 256 \times 7$
Bottleneck size	8192	$32 \times 32 \times 5$
CR	8	89.6
Loss function	SSIM	SSIM + RMSE

the Intel Movidius Myriad 2 VPU. The results for the VPU environment are obtained by running the encoder on the Intel Myriad 2 connected via USB to the local machine. The model must be preliminary converted using the OpenVINO toolkit [10]. This toolkit is specifically designed to optimize and deploy DL models for the supported Intel hardware platforms. Table 3 summarizes the performance in terms of power consumption, expressed in Watt (W), processing time, expressed in seconds (s), and energy efficiency, expressed as the ratio between the floating-point operations per second and the power consumption (FLOPS per Watt). Model size, after the optimization with OpenVINO, is also reported. The processing time is the time required by the application to compress a single band of the acquisition that was computed for the 3D model as the total processing time divided by the number of the processed bands. The efficiency between the 2D and 3D model is almost comparable, slightly better for the 2D model that shown a higher number of FLOPS and a lower processing time.

Results

The compression is a lossy compression. Results are evaluated here in terms of SSIM, which ranges between 0 and 1 [11]. In order to test the actual applicability of the reconstructed images, the algorithm performance was also evaluated in terms of application of the reconstructed images to common application cases. They include the detection of urban areas with a semantic segmentation algorithm based on a UNet Neural Network (NN) and the generation of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) maps. For the semantic segmentation, the trained UNet model is used to predict urban areas masks taking as input both the original and the decompressed image. Table 3 summarizes the performance in terms of SSIM and Hamming Distance (HD) for the semantic segmentation and NDVI tasks. The SSIM is computed as average value over all the patches belonging to the test set. HD is a pixel-based dissimilarity measure that ranges from 0 to 1. The results are almost identical.

As a quantitative comparison, the results obtained in terms of SSIM are compared with those obtained with JPEG 2000 algorithm. Indeed, JPEG 2000 is also used to compress independently the bands of Sentinel-2 multispectral images. The same input image was compressed with the CAE and with the JPEG 2000 algorithm, using a quality factor that returns a smaller image as much as the CAE CR, returning a 1.7% lower SSIM on average.

As a qualitative comparison, Fig. 5 shows for the 2D and the 3D models two test images with the corresponding reconstruction.

For the 3D model, the output of the encoder part can be represented as a multichannel image with 5 different bands representing the latent feature space, as shown in Fig. 6. Each image in the figure has a size of 512×512 , obtained by mosaicking each 32×32 patch to reconstruct the original input acquisition.

Table 3. Performance and results comparison for the 2D and 3D CAE models

		2D model	3D model
Performance	Power consumption	1.4 W	1.1 W
	Processing time	10.92 s	26.29 s
	Energy efficiency	0.008	0.006
	Model size	1.1 MB	53.25 KB
Results	SSIM	0.958	0.933
	Semantic segmentation (HD)	0.023	0.025
	NDVI (HD)	0.016	0.010

Fig. 5. Original and reconstructed test images. The red boxes indicate the location of the zoomed in areas shown below

Fig. 6. Encoder output. The output of the encoder part of the CAE can be represented as a multichannel image with 5 bands

CONCLUSION

The results obtained shown that the AE-based algorithms are capable to reduce the size of the input without a significant loss in key information. In the first application, this is demonstrated through the change detection application. The superior capability of AEs in reconstructing images compared with other well-known techniques, such as the DWT, is shown. Furthermore, the AE model is a fully connected network that could be run on-board because the computing resources and the memory required to store the training weights are comparable to those available in this context. In the second application, a 2D and a 3D CAE-based compression algorithms are presented. The algorithms are developed for the Φ sat-2 mission, and therefore considering the constraints related to the resources available on-board and the compatibility with the particular framework. The 2D CAE reduces the acquisition size by 8 times, while the 3D model by 89.6 with a limited information loss, as proved by the results evaluated in terms of SSIM and applicability of the decompressed images. Indeed, they were tested in applicative cases, such as semantic segmentation for detecting urban areas. The encoder part of the CAE has a size that allows to update the model even during the in-orbit operation phase of the mission. The models were tested on the Intel Myriad 2 VPU, that is the actual on-board hardware. Results evaluated in terms of image quality metrics and in the applicative scenarios of semantic segmentation and NDVI maps calculation revealed that reconstructed images can be used with comparable performance.

Further research will be focused to upgrade the model by reducing the number of units and target bands in the bottleneck layer for the 2D and 3D models, thus increasing the compression factor. Additionally, we aim to conduct a thorough comparison of the models with other existing AE-based algorithms for compressing and reconstructing multispectral satellite images.

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